

INELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF T300 / 5222 (C / E) COMPOSITE LAMINATE WITH CROSS PLYS

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the inelastic behaviour (particularly the non-linear viscoelasticity) of T300 / 5222 composite laminate by experimental and theoretical research. Experimental results of creep, stress relaxation and history-dependent stress-strain curves at different temperature levels are reported. Both loading and unloading processes are included. The locally averaged constitutive functionals are established on the basis of rational thermodynamics in our theoretical consideration. A Non-linear creep constitutive equation are constructed using the experimental data. A good agreement is arrived at between the experimental results and the corresponding analytic predictions.

Keywords: composite laminate, non-linear viscoelasticity, thermodynamics, creep

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of inelastic behaviours of composite materials has increasingly absorbed attentions of engineers in the consideration of optimum structural design and safty analysis to limit loading. As a matter of fact, many composite materials behave inelastically even at quite low levels of loads, especially when the temperature involved is elevated.

The present research work is concerned with the inelastic behaviour of T300 / 5222 composite laminate with cross-ply at different temperatures. This material, as is believed, may exhibite to be of elasticity, viscoelasticity and viscoplasticity as well as viscoelastoplasticity, or more complicated characteristics with presence of damage in the material when distinct thermal and / or mechanical loadings are involved. Our study here, however, reports only some results limited to the scale of 20°C ~ 80°C and 0~ 100MPa, within which the material behave viscoelastically and no plastic or damaged phenomena were observed. The further discussion about the viscoplastic and damage behaviour of the material will be performed in another report by the authors. Nevertheless, an examination of the experimental data reveals many interesting results, such as path-dependent creep and fading memory, etc.. In order to describe correctly those physical phenomena and to construct reasonable constitutive relations, we employ a locally averaged thermodynamical framework based on the thermodynamics theory proposed by Coleman^[1] and Noll^[2] for materials with mem-

ory, and finally determine the material coefficients by fitting the experimental data.

In § 2 typical experimental results are illustrated, and upon them a detailed discussion which analyzes qualitatively the characteristics of the inelastic behaviour is conducted. Parts of fitted constitutive equations are given in § 3, and in § 4 we make some brief concluding remarks for the results obtained.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental work was completed with MTS880-50KN material testing system. Uniaxial stress-controlled or strain-controlled stress-strain curves can be automatically recorded by the testing system, and some typical results are illustrated in Fig.1~Fig.6.

A representative stress-controlled strain-stress curve is shown in Fig.1 under the conditions that the temperature involved is at 60°C, and the stress is applied in the direction of +45° / -45° of the laminate with ± 2.29MPa / S of stress rate. The loop formed by the curve after a loading-unloading cycle shows an inelastic behaviour with irreversible dissipation. One may notice that the strain does not vanish immediately while the stress applied returns to a stress-free state. The varying of the residual strain (denoted by OB in Figure 1) need be investigated carefully since its characteristic is of key importance in determining if there exists an irreversible deformation associated with plasticity or damage processes. It is shown in Fig.2 that the residual strain decreases gradually with past of the time and would vanish completely when the time $t \rightarrow \infty$ (say, after 16h in practical tests). The facts described in Fig.1 and Fig.2 imply that the dynamic response of the material subject to a thermal or mechanical perturbation would eventually approach an equilibrium state, which, as is known, is one of the effects of viscoelasticity featuring fading memory.

Fig.1. stress-strain curve at 60°C. The direction of the laminate subject to external load is +45° / -45°, and the stress rate is ± 2.29 MPa / s

Fig.2. recovery of the residual strain. The result during 600 seconds is illustrated in the Figure

Another experimental result is shown in Fig.3 which could be used to examine on the other hand whether there is damage in the material under study. This test is conducted in twice for the same a laminate under the same condition as in Fig.1, but one is done 16h after another. The coincidence

of the twice experimental data shows there is no apparent loss of the creep modulus and so no damage occurs.

By using those creep and relaxation curves, particularly their asymptotic properties as the time $t \rightarrow \infty$, we can get the useful information about the elastic effect coupled with the viscoelastic features, since the characteristic of fading memory which the material possesses guarantees that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon(t) = \hat{\varepsilon}^{(e)}(\sigma^e, T),$$

or

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(t) = \hat{\sigma}^{(e)}(\varepsilon^e, T) \quad (1)$$

of which $\varepsilon(t)$ and $\sigma(t)$ denote respectively the dynamic strain and stress responses when the material subjected to an external action, ε^e and σ^e are the initial strain and stress of an equilibrium state before the material is disturbed, and T represents the temperature. Obviously, the equilibrium

Fig.3. Experimental data of twice tests for one laminate, one is 16h after another. The temperature is 60° , the direction of the laminate subject to external loads is $+45^\circ / -45^\circ$ with $\pm 2.29\text{MPa} / \text{S}$ of stress rate.

Fig.4. Creep curves (illustrated by AA', BB' and CC') at 60°C in the direction of $+45^\circ / -45^\circ$ of the laminate. The curve OABC describes a stress-controlled loading process.

Fig.5. Stress relaxation curves (illustrated by AA', BB', CC', DD' and EE') at 60°C in the direction of $+45^\circ / -45^\circ$ of the laminate. The curve OABCDE describes a strain-controlled loading process.

responses of materials are elastic^[3]. Then, if we choose a series of different equilibrium stresses σ_k^e or strains ε_k^e ($k = 1, 2, \dots$), and let $\Delta\varepsilon^e = \varepsilon_{k+1}^e - \varepsilon_k^e$ be a constant for each k ($k = 1, 2, \dots$), we can determine the elastic behaviour of the material in accordance with the relationship expressed by eqn.(1). In fact, if the elastic effect of the material is linear, a linear dependence of $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Delta\varepsilon_k(t)$ on

$\Delta\sigma_k^e$ or $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Delta\sigma_k(t)$ on $\Delta\varepsilon_k^e$ will be observed, or else the elastic effect of the material would be non-linear. Analyses of results shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5 indicate that the elastic effect of the material is non-linear, but the non-linearity is not strong which can be estimated by examining how strong the term $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon(t)$ depends on σ^e , or alternatively, the term $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(t)$ does on E^e . This conclusion, of course, is valid only under the present experimental condition. Thus, we utilize the thermodynamic functional

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(t) = & g(T) + \frac{1}{2} C_{ijkl} \sigma_{ik} \sigma_{jl} + \frac{1}{3} D_{ijklmn} \sigma_{ji} \sigma_{lk} \sigma_{nm} + \int_0^\infty E_{ij}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_{ji}'}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \eta_{ij}(\tau) I_{ij} \frac{dT'}{d\tau} d\tau \\
 & + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \beta_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{dT'}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\sigma_{ji}'}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \gamma_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) I_{ji} \frac{dT'}{d\tau_1} \frac{dT'}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\
 & + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \Omega_{ijkl}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{d\sigma_{jk}'}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\sigma_{lk}'}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

of (a-3) in the Appendix to describe the behaviour of the material with non-linear elastic effect and fading memory. Here, as is declared in the Appendix, $G(t)$ is the Gibbs free energy, σ_{ij} and T denote the stress and temperature, $i, j, k, l, m, n = 1, 2, 3$, respectively, t indicates the current time and τ the dummy one, the remaining quantities are material coefficients or functions. All physical quantities are locally averaged and here all bars appeared in (a-3) of the Appdix have been discarded for the sake of convenience.

Correspondingly, the strain functional can be obtain from the eqn. (a-4) of the Appendix

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(t) = \varepsilon_{ij}^0 + C_{ijkl} \sigma_{lk} + D_{ijklmn} \sigma_{lk} \sigma_{nm} + \int_0^\infty \beta_{ij}(\tau) \frac{dT'}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \Omega_{ijkl}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_{lk}'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

3. CREEP CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

We may recast the eqn.(3) into the more common form

$$\varepsilon_j = \varepsilon_j^0 + C_{kj} \sigma_k + D_{ikj} \sigma_k \sigma_i + \int_0^\infty \beta_j(\tau) \frac{dT'}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \Omega_{mj} \frac{d\sigma_m'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (4)$$

used preferably in practice for composite material laminates^{[4][5]} with the notation of the Voigt subscripts which make the i, j, k and m are equal to 1 to 6, respectively, when a general 3-dimensional case is concerned, and take respectively 1, 2 and 6 only for the in-plane case of the laminate. For the latter case and with the consideration that the tension and shear effects are decoupling, we have

$$\varepsilon_1(t) = \alpha_{11} \sigma_1 + \alpha_{12} \sigma_2 + \beta_{111} \sigma_1 \sigma_1 + \beta_{112} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \beta_{122} \sigma_2 \sigma_2$$

$$+ \int_0^{\infty} \Omega_{11}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_1'}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^{\infty} \Omega_{12}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_2'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_2(t) = \alpha_{21}\sigma_1 + \alpha_{22}\sigma_2 + \beta_{211}\sigma_1\sigma_1 + \beta_{221}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + \beta_{222}\sigma_2\sigma_2$$

$$+ \int_0^{\infty} \Omega_{21}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_1'}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^{\infty} \Omega_{22}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_2'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_6(t) = \alpha_{66}\sigma_6 + \beta_{666}\sigma_6\sigma_6 + \int_0^{\infty} \Omega_{66}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_6'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (7)$$

in the on-axis co-ordinates and constant temperature histories. The symmetry of the laminate with cross-ply further requires

$$\alpha_{11} = \alpha_{22}, \alpha_{12} = \alpha_{21}, \beta_{112} = \beta_{221}, \beta_{111} = \beta_{222}, \\ \beta_{122} = \beta_{211}, \Omega_{11}(\tau) = \Omega_{22}(\tau), \Omega_{21}(\tau) = \Omega_{12}(\tau).$$

All the material coefficients could be determined through a numerical technique of fitting experimental data. Especially, a proper utilization of the forms of the constitutive relations in off-axis co-ordinates may make it more convenient in determining some of these coefficients. For instance, in the case that only uniaxial loading-unloading processes is involved we have

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_{11} + \alpha_{12} + \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{66})\sigma_x + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_{111} + \beta_{112} + \beta_{222} + \frac{1}{2}\beta_{666})\sigma_x^2 \\ + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} [\Omega_{11}(\tau) + \Omega_{12}(\tau) + \Omega_{66}(\tau)] \frac{d\sigma_x'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon_y = \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_{11} + \alpha_{12} - \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{66})\sigma_x + \frac{1}{4}(\beta_{111} + \beta_{112} + \beta_{222} - \frac{1}{2}\beta_{666})\sigma_x^2 \\ + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} [\Omega_{11}(\tau) + \Omega_{12}(\tau) - \Omega_{66}(\tau)] \frac{d\sigma_x'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (9)$$

$$\varepsilon_{xy} = 0 \quad (10)$$

where ε_x , ε_y and ε_{xy} denote the strains in an off-axis co-ordinates with $\pm 45^\circ$ off-angles, and σ_x is the uniaxial stress in the same co-ordinates. And eqn.(8)-eqn.(9) yields

$$\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y = \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{66}\sigma_x + \frac{1}{4}\beta_{666}\sigma_x^2 + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \Omega_{66}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_x'}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (11)$$

As both ε_x and ε_y are available in a uniaxial test with MTS materials testing system, we may determine α_{66}, β_{666} and $\Omega_{66}(\tau)$, as is indicated in eqn.(11), with a uniaxial tension curve instead of shear tests. Some fitted α_{66}, β_{666} and $\Omega_{66}(\tau)$ are listed as follows

$$\alpha_{66} = \begin{cases} 0.132 \times 10^{-5} (MPa)^{-1}, & \text{at } 20^\circ\text{C} \\ 0.156 \times 10^{-5} (MPa)^{-1}, & \text{at } 60^\circ\text{C} \\ 0.198 \times 10^{-5} (MPa)^{-1}, & \text{at } 80^\circ\text{C} \end{cases} \quad \beta_{666} = \begin{cases} 0.415 \times 10^{-6} (MPa)^{-2}, & \text{at } 20^\circ\text{C} \\ 0.634 \times 10^{-6} (MPa)^{-2}, & \text{at } 60^\circ\text{C} \\ 0.173 \times 10^{-6} (MPa)^{-2}, & \text{at } 80^\circ\text{C} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Omega_{66}(\tau) = 3.35 \times 10^{-6} [1 - e^{-\frac{\tau}{10.11(sec)}}] \left\{ 1 + \text{sgn}[\dot{\sigma}_x(\tau)] \right\} \\ + 2.71 \times 10^{-6} [1 - e^{-\frac{\tau}{4.05(sec)}}] \left\{ 1 - \text{sgn}[\dot{\sigma}_x(\tau)] \right\} (MPa)^{-1}, \text{ when at } 20^\circ\text{C} \quad (12)$$

$$\Omega_{66}(\tau) = 2.20 \times 10^{-6} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{\tau}{9694.37(sec)}} \right] \left\{ 1 + sgn[\dot{\sigma}_x(\tau)] \right\} + 7.13 \times 10^{-6} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{\tau}{7.14(sec)}} \right] \left\{ 1 - sgn[\dot{\sigma}_x(\tau)] \right\} (MPa)^{-1}, \text{ when at } 60^\circ\text{C} \quad (13)$$

$$\Omega_{66}(\tau) = 5.98 \times 10^{-6} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{\tau}{28189.16(sec)}} \right] \left\{ 1 + sgn[\dot{\sigma}_x(\tau)] \right\} + 5.52 \times 10^{-6} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{\tau}{8.08(sec)}} \right] \left\{ 1 - sgn[\dot{\sigma}_x(\tau)] \right\} (MPa)^{-1}, \text{ when at } 80^\circ\text{C} \quad (14)$$

Note that the kernel functions $\Omega_{66}(\tau)$ expressed in (12)~(14) satisfy the requirements of fading memories. In addition, the explicit dependence of all coefficients upon temperature could be obtained by interpolation technique if it is needed.

4. DISCUSSIONS

In Fig.6 we depict the comparisons of the fitted expression (11) with the corresponding experimental data. It is shown that analytical predictions are satisfactory as compared with the experimental results. It can also be seen from (12)~(14) that the creep modulus are different even at the same temperature. The dependence of creep modulus on the paths of loading-unloading processes demonstrate a strong non-linearity of material. Besides, the temperature-dependence of the characteristic retardent time τ is also strongly path-dependent upon the loading-unloading processes. One may notice from the expressions of (12)~(14) that τ changes from 10.11(sec) to 28289.16(sec) from 20°C to 80°C in a loading process, but varies merely from 4.05 (sec) to 8.08 (sec) in an unloading process when the material undergoing the same temperature variation. Such a property of τ is scarcely reported in previous works, and so far its microscopically physical mechanism remains unknown to us. A further detailed analysis to the experimental data shows that there exists no a direct time-temperature equivalency as indicated by the famous empirical formulation known as WLF relation^[6] for τ and T (temperature) in both loading and unloading processes. And it can be readily shown that the non-linear elastic effect does not surpass 10% compared with the linear elastic contribution.

Fig.6. Comparisons of analytical Predictions with experimental data at 20°C, 60°C and 80°C.

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APPENDIX

Suppose that the local thermodynamic functional Gibbs free energy $G(t)$ of materials can be expressed as

$$G(t) = G^I(\sigma_{ij}, T) + \int_0^\infty E_{ij}(\tau) \frac{d\sigma_{ji}^I}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \eta_{ij}(\tau) I_{ji} \frac{dT^I}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \beta_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{dT^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\sigma_{ji}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \gamma_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) I_{ji} \frac{dT^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\sigma_{ji}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \Omega_{klj}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{d\sigma_{kl}^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{dT^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \dots \quad (a-1)$$

where E_{ij} , η_{ij} , β_{ij} , γ_{ij} and Ω_{klj} ($i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3$) are material coefficients, I_{ij} is the unit tensor. Integral of (a-1) over the volume of a representative volume of the composite material laminate yields

$$\bar{G}(t) = \bar{G}^I(\bar{\sigma}_{ij}, \bar{T}) + \int_0^\infty \bar{E}_{ij}(\tau) \frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{ji}^I}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \bar{\eta}_{ij}(\tau) I_{ji} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \bar{\beta}_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{ji}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \bar{\gamma}_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) I_{ji} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{ji}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \bar{\Omega}_{klj}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{kl}^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \dots \quad (a-2)$$

Where quantities with bars denote the locally averaged ones. It should be pointed out that the average material coefficients such as \bar{E}_{ij} , etc., are dependent on the stress and temperature fluctuations of space as well as their boundary integrations, hence, they are non-local in essence. However, it is assumed that all the integrals related to the volume converges rapidly on the remote boundary of the element, so that we can regard the average thermodynamic functional to be local in a macroscopic scale concerned. From the local dissipative inequality

$$-\rho(\dot{G} + S\dot{T}) - \dot{\sigma}_{ij} \varepsilon_{ji} - \frac{1}{T} q_i g_i \geq 0$$

of which ρ represents the local density, g_i and q_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are the temperature gradient and

heat flux, respectively, we have correspondingly

$$-\overline{\rho(\dot{G} + \dot{S}T)} - \overline{\dot{\sigma}_{ij} \bar{\varepsilon}_{ji}} - \left[\left(\overline{S \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta T} \right) + \left(\overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ji}} \right) \right] - \left(\frac{1}{T} q_i g_i \right) \geq 0 \quad (a-3)$$

where δ is a spatial fluctuation operator. Substitution of (a-2) into (a-3) yields

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} = -\bar{E}_{ij}(0) - \frac{\partial \bar{G}^I}{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{ij}} - \int_0^\infty \bar{\beta}_{ij}(\tau_1, 0) \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_1} d\tau_1 - \int_0^\infty \bar{\Omega}_{klij}(\tau_1, 0) \frac{d\bar{\sigma}'_{ik}}{d\tau_1} d\tau_1 + \dots \quad (a-4)$$

$$\bar{S} = -\bar{\eta}_{ij}(0) I_{ji} - \frac{\partial \bar{G}^I}{\partial T} - \int_0^\infty \bar{\beta}_{ij}(\tau_1, 0) \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_1} d\tau_1 - \int_0^\infty \bar{\gamma}_{ij}(\tau_1, 0) I_{ji} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_1} d\tau_1 + \dots \quad (a-5)$$

using the method of [1]. And (a-3) is reduced to

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Lambda}_d = & \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{E}_{ij}(\tau) \frac{d\bar{\sigma}'_{ji}}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\eta}_{ij}(\tau) I_{ji} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau} d\tau + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\Omega}_{klij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{d\bar{\sigma}'_{ik}}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\bar{\sigma}'_{jl}}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\ & + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\gamma}_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) I_{ji} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 + \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \bar{\beta}_{ij}(\tau_1, \tau_2) \frac{d\bar{\sigma}'_{ji}}{d\tau_1} \frac{d\bar{T}^I}{d\tau_2} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \\ & + \left[\left(\overline{S \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta T} \right) + \left(\overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \delta \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ji}} \right) \right] - \left(\frac{1}{T} q_i g_i \right) + \dots \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$